

Event Abstract

Medical education in the time of COVID-19: A Libyan view

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The global spread of COVID-19 pandemic had carried a serious implication for public institutions and particularly for educational institutes. This has prompted a series of public health worries. University closures are considering among the community distancing actions used by policy makers to reduce the spread of an infectious disease. These closures are based on the response to reduce public contacts between students and thus disturb the disease transmission. Many countries in the world have started a countrywide educational institute closure, with the goal of averting contacts among students and hence reduce cases.

In response to this concern, the ministry of education in Libya had implemented national school closures by March 15, 2020, and this interruption might extend as the COVID-19 pandemic continues to progress, which could lead to students missing their classes, producing a negative consequence on the learning process and exam concert. Indeed, there is a substantial number of students undertaking examination that require social contact and exposure.

Consequently, numerous education institutes in Libya had started online learning tactics by using the academic online platforms to stay linked with their students. For example, the Research, Consultant and Training Center (RCC) of the University of Tripoli (UOT), Libya has instructed their students and academicians to get benefit from the existing online resources to finalize their teaching duties.

With the use of the MS Office 365, the RCC of the UOT guided the necessary training for students and staff members to enable them for using applications which found within that platform, and which can assist in online learning like MS Teams, MS OneDrive, MS Class Notebook and other applications. Other method considered by the UOT is to take benefit of initiatives for learning online in response to covid-19 from many institutes like from Coursera which offers a free access to more than 3,800 courses from leading universities and corporations. RCC manage the registration of

UOT students in Coursera system and evaluate the performance of the learning process.

With the certainty that social distancing activities might stay for many months or even years, there is a decisive need to identify how countries can safely return students to education. Once the number of covid-19 cases starts to decline, the arrangements used to achieve suppression might evolve over time. It will be crucial for studies to screen the consequence of the reopening of the educational institutes on the numbers of covid-19 cases. Academicians as well as policy makers should get elaborated in exploring other institutes social distancing interventions that are much less disruptive than completely university closure and might effectively evolved to preserving the control of this pandemic. Explorative researches are warrant to guide decision-makers on the opening of universities once the deadly pandemic declines.

Keywords: RCC, UOT, Education, Covid-19.

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